

Investigation of micro- and mesomixing in a reaction mixing pump

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Abstract

The present study investigates the application of a reaction mixing pump (RMP) as a reactor for mixing-sensitive reactions. In a RMP, the effect of impeller speed and feed rate ratios on the selectivity of the Villermaux-Dushman (VD) reaction system was investigated through experimental means. The observations revealed three distinct mixing regimes, namely backmixing, micromixing and mesomixing, which were dependent on the feed ratio. Increasing impeller speed led to an increase in the selectivity of desired products in the micro- and mesomixing regimes, while it had

the opposite effect in the backmixing regime. In the backmixing and mesomixing regimes, selectivity was sensitive to alterations in feed ratio; conversely, in the micromixing regime, changes in feed ratio did not affect the selectivity significantly. In addition, the engulfment micromixing model was utilised to predict selectivities in the micromixing regime, demonstrating a strong correlation with the experimental data. For the first time, the W-Z-transformation was applied to the VD reaction system within the context of the engulfment model. High energy dissipation rates resulted in a reduction of the mixing times to the order of magnitude of 10^{-3} s. This was accompanied by an increase in the selectivity of desired products in the micromixing regime. These observations emphasize the efficiency of RMPs as a promising class of reactors for reactions that are sensitive to mixing.

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1. Introduction

Many syntheses are often accompanied by side reactions in which unwanted side-products are formed. The formation of side-products is an inefficient use of raw materials and it reduces the yield of the target product. Furthermore, in many cases it necessitates separation processes downstream of the reactor to obtain the target product with high purity. Achieving higher selectivities to target products in such syntheses is an economically and environmentally important goal. This goal can be achieved not only by chemical means, such as the use of catalysis, but also by physical means, such as the manipulation of mixing intensity, reactor type, and the rate and location of the feed of reactants [1].

The present study focuses on the process of reactant mixing and its influence on the rate of reaction and the product distribution. According to Baldyga *et al.* [2], the mixing of chemicals in reactors can be categorized into three distinct scales: macromixing, mesomixing, and micromixing. Macromixing is defined as the homogenization of concentration gradients of the reacting species at the scale of the equipment (the reactor) [3]. In contrast, micromixing can be regarded as the process of mixing of different species at the molecular level [4–7]. The process of mesomixing occurs between these two scales in the region near the feed point of reactants where a plume of fresh feed can be formed [2, 6]. Given that reactions between different species occur at the molecular level and that the reactants must be fed into the reactor, in principle, it is necessary to take micro- and mesomixing into consideration in each study of reactions in a given reactor. Nevertheless, for a considerable number of syntheses, the time constant of the reaction rates is found to be higher than the time constant of the micromixing and mesomixing processes. Therefore, these syntheses are solely influenced by macromixing. This means that the mixture is homogenized at the molecular level, and the macroscopic observable concentration profiles of the reacting species within the reactor influence the rates of reactions. This class of reaction systems is frequently designated as "kinetically controlled reactions" [1]. In this work, however, we address another class of reaction systems: the "mixing-sensitive" or "mixing-controlled reactions" [1]. This class of reaction systems is found when the time constant of a reaction is in the same order of magnitude as or less than the time constant for mixing the reactants at the meso and micro scale. While the majority of syntheses are classified as belonging to the first category, numerous industrially significant reaction systems exhibit a high degree of sensitivity to mixing [1, 8, 9]. If a given synthesis is sensitive to mixing, both the reactor design and the process conditions (e.g. feed rates) must be carefully chosen to ensure rapid mixing of the reactants after entering the reactor at the feed point and thus to achieve high selectivity to the target products.

In the past, many different reactor types have been proposed for mixing-sensitive reactions. A detailed review on reactors for mixing-sensitive reactions can be found in [10]. In principle, two different categories of mixers (reactors) are used: static and active mixers. Examples, for static

mixer designs that are suitable for mixing sensitive reactions are Kenics [11, 12], SMV/SMX [12–14], and T- or V-shaped static mixers [15, 16]. The stirred tank equipped with an impeller is an example of a reactor that applies active mixing [17, 18]. Another example for an active mixer is the rotor-stator spinning disk reactor (rs-SDR) presented by Manzano Martínez *et al.* [6]. This reactor features a rotating disk encased within a stationary cylindrical housing, creating a high-shear environment that generates intense turbulence and, consequently, effective mixing of the reactants. They observed short mixing times and high selectivities of desired products in this reactor. Following the conclusions of [6], we hypothesize that Reaction Mixing Pumps (RMPs) are also well suited for mixing-sensitive reaction systems due to their special design, which generates high turbulence within the pump. RMPs are a form of peripheral pumps that work similarly to side channel pumps. They feature an impeller with numerous small vanes machined into both sides of its outer edge. This impeller rotates adjacent to a concentric channel within the casing. The interaction of the liquid with the rotating blades of the impeller and the side channels forces the liquid elements into a spiral-shaped flow trajectory. Consequently, the fluid undergoes numerous circulations between the impeller and the side channel as it moves from the pump inlet to the outlet. Moreover, the unique configuration of the impeller leads to the circulation of fluid along its circumference, thereby inducing high internal recirculation flow rates [19]. Due to their reduced volume in comparison to conventional stirred tank reactors, it is anticipated that RMPs will achieve effective macroscopic mixing. Furthermore, the RMPs exhibit a low pump efficiency, leading to a high volumetric energy dissipation within the reaction mixing pump. This property is particularly advantageous for micromixing behavior. Additionally, RMPs combine mixing and transport of the reaction media and thereby leading to a process intensification. In summary, the reaction mixing pump is a potentially viable reactor type for fast mixing-sensitive reactions.

To demonstrate the applicability of the RMP as a reactor for mixing-sensitive reactions, we investigated the product distribution of the Villermaux-Dushman (VD) reaction system under various conditions in a RMP. This reaction has been utilized in numerous studies in conjunction with a variety of reactors, such as stirred tank reactors [20, 21], milli- and microflow reactors [22, 23], jet reactors [24, 25], and rotor-stator spinning disc reactors [6, 26]. Consequently, it serves as a valuable tool for assessing the mixing performance of the RMP in comparison to other reactors. Moreover, a comprehensive kinetic model for this reaction system has been documented in the literature [27], thereby enabling modeling and simulation studies. This reaction is also a suitable test reaction due to its straightforward UV spectrophotometric analysis and cost-effectiveness [28].

In this study, the impeller speed of the RMP and feed rate ratios were systematically varied. In addition to the experimental investigations, the well-established engulfment model proposed by Bałdyga *et al.* [29] was employed to model the micromixing behavior within the reactor. This model was chosen for its simplicity and its widespread recognition in the field, making it particularly suitable for the present application. In this work, the engulfment model was utilized for two primary purposes: first, to predict the influence of process parameters on the product distribution within the micromixing regime, and second, to calculate theoretical mixing times based on the experimental results. The W-Z-transformation was applied to the Villermaux-Dushman reaction system within the framework of the engulfment model for the first time. A comparison of the simulated values with the experimental results indicates that the selectivities

in the reaction system are determined exclusively by the micromixing process over a wide range of operating conditions.

2. Theory

2.1. Villermaux-Dushman reaction

The Villermaux-Dushman (VD) reaction is a system of competitive parallel reactions that includes an instantaneous neutralization reaction (Reaction (I)), a fast iodide-iodate reaction (Reaction (II)), and an equilibrium iodine-iodide reaction (Reaction (III)). The third reaction produces triiodide ions, which can be detected using a UV-vis spectrometer at a wavelength of 353 nm [20, 21, 28, 30–33].

Under ideal mixing conditions, the neutralization reaction immediately consumes all available acid, thereby minimizing the occurrence of iodine-iodide reaction and resulting in negligible levels of triiodide ions. However, in cases of poor mixing, localized concentrations of acid form, allowing the neutralization reaction to partially consume the acid and enabling iodide-iodate reaction to proceed, yielding iodine. Subsequent detection of the iodine is accomplished via UV-vis spectroscopy as triiodide ions, which are formed in Reaction (III). Thus, the concentration of the triiodide ions is a measure of the mixing performance [28]. The kinetic model of the VD reaction system is available in Supplementary Material S.1.

2.2. Engulfment Model

The engulfment model proposed by Bałdyga *et al.* [29] is a theoretical micromixing model that describes the influence of the local energy dissipation rate and the kinetic viscosity on micromixing behavior [34]. It operates under the assumption that for Schmidt numbers below 4000, micromixing behavior is primarily governed by the entrainment of fluid into turbulent vortices, a process known as engulfment. This assumption is applicable to the present investigations, which involve aqueous solutions with estimated Schmidt numbers in the range of approximately 100 to 1000.

Based on the underlying assumption that engulfment is the controlling mechanism, the engulfment model describes the growth of a reaction zone as bulk fluid is engulfed into the fresh feed. The growth of this volume is ruled by the engulfment rate E , which is given by Equation (2.1) [29]. The concept of the engulfment model is sketched in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1.: Concept of the engulfment model. The reactor is divided into a growing reaction zone and a surrounding bulk phase.

$$E = 0.05776\sqrt{\epsilon/\nu} \quad (2.1)$$

In Equation (2.1), ν is the kinematic viscosity of the fluid and ϵ is the local energy dissipation rate [29]. Considering the effect of self engulfment, the volume fraction $X^{(1)}$ of the reaction zone increases over the life time α and can be calculated by Equation (2.2) [35].

$$\frac{dX^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = EX^{(1)}(1 - X^{(1)}) \quad (2.2)$$

The volume fraction of the reaction zone is defined by Equation (2.3). Here $V^{(1)}$ represents the increasing volume of the reaction zone and $V^{(0)}$ denotes the total reactor volume.

$$X^{(1)} = \frac{V^{(1)}}{V^{(0)}} \quad (2.3)$$

Based on Equation (2.2), the change of concentration of a substance i in the reaction zone is described by Equation (2.4) [35].

$$\frac{dc_i^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E(1 - X^{(1)})(c_i^{(2)} - c_i^{(1)}) + R_i \quad (2.4)$$

Here, $c_i^{(1)}$ is the concentration of substance i in the growing reaction zone and $c_i^{(2)}$ is the concentration of substance i in the surrounding bulk phase which is engulfed into the reaction zone. R_i is the reaction term of species i inside the reaction zone [29]. Equation (2.4) describes the dilution and subsequent reaction of a single fluid element of the acid feed within a surrounding

bulk phase.

In this work, the RMP is modeled as an ideal continuous stirred tank reactor (CSTR) based on the assumptions that micromixing is rate-limiting and that macroscopic flow behavior, i.e., large internal circulation flows, causes negligible macroscopic concentration gradients within the RMP. This assumption was confirmed by comparing the residence time behavior of the RMP in tracer experiments with the predictions of the CSTR model in our previous work [36]. To account for micromixing, the dynamic simulation approach proposed by Bourne *et al.* [37][35] is adapted, which enables the application of the engulfment model within a CSTR framework. In this approach, the continuous feeds (in this work, acid and buffer flows in the Villermaux-Dushman reaction system) are discretized into finite fluid elements. The volumes of the acid and buffer elements, $\Delta V^{(1)}$ and $\Delta V^{(2)}$, are determined by a macroscopic time step Δt , as described in Equation (2.5) and Equation (2.6).

$$\Delta V^{(1)} = \Delta t \dot{V}^{(1)} \quad (2.5)$$

$$\Delta V^{(2)} = \Delta t \dot{V}^{(2)} \quad (2.6)$$

Here, $\dot{V}^{(1)}$ and $\dot{V}^{(2)}$ denote the flow rates of the acid and buffer streams, respectively, as illustrated in Figure 2.2. The fluid elements are introduced sequentially into the reactor, or more precisely,

Figure 2.2.: Flow rates and concentrations in the reaction mixing pump.

into the bulk phase. First, an acid element k is introduced into the system. For this element, the ODE system resulting from Equation (2.4) and Equation (2.2) is solved over the interval $\alpha_k = 0$ to $\alpha_{k,\text{end}} = \Delta t$. This approach assumes that all relevant reactions are completed within the duration of the time step, which imposes a lower limit on the value of Δt . In this case, suitable values for Δt for the combination of the VD system with the RMP range between approximately 0.01 s and 0.1 s. Throughout this calculation, the concentrations of the different species i in the bulk phase are considered constant.

After this, the corresponding buffer fluid element is introduced into the reactor. The concen-

trations of the fully reacted acid zone, the freshly added buffer, and the remaining bulk phase are then averaged to determine the updated bulk concentrations for the subsequent feed element $k + 1$, as described by Equation (2.7).

$$c_{i,k+1}^{(2)} = c_{i,k}^{(2)} \left(1 - X_k^{(1)}(\alpha_{k,\text{end}}) - \frac{\Delta V^{(2)}}{V^{(0)}} \right) + c_i^{(2)\text{in}} \frac{\Delta V^{(2)}}{V^{(0)}} + c_{i,k}^{(1)}(\alpha_{k,\text{end}}) X_k^{(1)}(\alpha_{k,\text{end}}) \quad (2.7)$$

This procedure is repeated iteratively until steady-state concentrations are reached at the reactor outlet. The chemical components of the acid and buffer flows in the VD reaction system are provided in Section 3.

It should be noted that the dynamic simulation approach used in this work is identical to the one proposed by Bourne *et al.* [37]. However, the main difference lies in the formulation of the governing equation: while Bourne *et al.* [37] applied a dimensionless form, this study employs the dimensional form of Equation (2.7). The derivation of this equation is provided in Supplementary Material S.8.

The described approach is also applied to estimate micromixing times based on the experimental data. By correlating the engulfment rate E in Equation (2.4) with the micromixing time t_{mix} via Equation (2.8), an inverse function can be obtained that relates the micromixing time to the experimentally measured selectivities.

$$E = \frac{1}{t_{\text{mix}}} \quad (2.8)$$

It is worth mentioning that the reliability of the calculated micromixing times critically depends on the validity of the underlying modeling assumptions [38].

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Experimental Setup

Figure 3.1 shows the experimental setup, which comprises the reaction mixing pump (P1). The investigated RMP was a type of peripheral pump comprising a teflon impeller (with a diameter of 0.03 m and a maximum impeller speed of 61 rps), surrounded on both sides by side channels. The RMP is cooled by the transported fluid. Since the pump operates in continuous mode, its temperature is inherently regulated. To provide visual access to the interior of the pump, the original pump head was replaced with a pump head made of poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA). The reactor volume, defined as the free space between the inlet and outlet of the pump that can be filled with fluid, was measured to be 1.76 mL. The pump had two inlets for the reactants (buffer flow and acid flow) and one outlet for the products. The buffer solution (an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide, boric acid, potassium iodate, and potassium iodide) was stored in tank (B1). The acid solution (an aqueous solution of perchloric acid) was stored in tank (B2). The feed line of the buffer solution was equipped with a valve (V1), a flowmeter (F11), and a pressure sensor (PR1). To feed the acid solution into the RMP, a high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) pump (P2) was employed. The product line was equipped with a thermocouple (TI1) and a pressure sensor (PR2). Both pressure sensors measured the absolute pressure. A needle valve (V2) was installed to regulate the pressure drop in the product line. The product was collected either in a waste tank (B3) or in sample vials, which were used for measuring the concentration of triiodide. The data obtained from the sensors (PR1), (PR2), and (TI1) were recorded by a data logger. A high-speed camera (HSC) and a LED light source was positioned in front of the RMP to record videos. These videos were used to calculate the actual rotational speed of the impeller. The details of the components of the experimental setup are available in Supplementary Material S.2. A figure showing the main dimensions of the RMP is available in Supplementary Material S.3.

3.2. Solution Preparation

For each experimental set (group of experiments conducted using the same batch of chemical stock solutions), a 25 L bulk solution was prepared with concentrations as outlined in Table 3.1. All solutions were prepared using deionized water sparged with nitrogen to remove its dissolved oxygen. This precaution was taken because dissolved oxygen can convert iodide ions to iodine [21]. Additionally, a specific protocol [26, 39] was employed to suppress iodine formation during solution preparation. The process began with adding 5 L of boric acid to 5 L of sodium hydroxide solution, resulting in the formation of an equimolar mixture of H_2BO_3^- and $\text{B}(\text{OH})_3$ with a pH

Figure 3.1.: Experimental setup and reaction mixing pump used in this study.

of 9.14. At this moderately alkaline pH, iodine formation is inhibited [21]. Subsequently, 5 L solutions of potassium iodide and potassium iodate were added to the buffer solution. The total volume was then adjusted to 25 L by adding a 5 L of water. To ensure homogeneity, the buffer solution was mixed thoroughly using a stirrer during preparation. The viscosity and density of the buffer solution at various temperatures, as measured by a Stabinger viscometer, are provided in Supplementary Material S.5. Perchloric acid was diluted with water to achieve the desired concentration, as illustrated in Table 3.1. In assessing micromixing performance using the VD reaction, sulfuric acid is conventionally utilized. However, this approach has a systematic problem. The second proton available for dissociation of sulfuric acid exhibits lower acidity than the first one, as exemplified by its pK_a values ($pK_{a1} = -3.00$, $pK_{a2} = 1.99$) [40–42]. As such, results obtained using sulfuric acid may not be reliable for short micromixing times. To overcome this limitation, perchloric acid was chosen due to its high strength as a monoprotic acid ($pK_a = -9.24$) [26, 27]. pK_a is the negative log of the acid dissociation constant.

Considering the potential for oxidation and sensitivity to light, the buffer and perchloric acid solutions were prepared immediately prior to the experiments and used on the same day to prevent degradation. Their exposure to direct light was also avoided [21, 26, 39]. Details of the suppliers and purities of the chemicals used are listed in Supplementary Material S.4.

Table 3.1.: Concentrations of bulk and acid solutions.

	compound	formula	concentration (mol L^{-1})
buffer solution	sodium hydroxide	NaOH	0.0060
	boric acid	$\text{B}(\text{OH})_3$	0.0120
	potassium iodate	KIO_3	0.0024
	potassium iodide	KI	0.0120
acid solution	perchloric acid	HClO_4	0.0500

3.3. Experimental procedure

3.3.1. Pump Characteristic Curve

In this work, the flow rate of the RMP (buffer solution) ranged from 4 to 26 L h⁻¹. Initially, the float-type flow meter (FI1) was calibrated using the buffer solution within this range to find a correlation between the float level and the buffer flow rates. Subsequently, the flow rates of 4, 11, 18, and 26 L h⁻¹ were selected to determine the pump characteristic curve. For each buffer flow rate, the desired impeller speed of the pump was first selected, and then the needle valve was adjusted to set the flow meter to the desired flow rate based on the calibration curve. After adjusting the buffer flow rate and reaching the steady state (approximately after two minutes), the flow rate was also measured by weighing the vessel of buffer solution before and after a specified period of time. Simultaneously, a video was recorded using the high-speed camera. Finally, the pressures at the inlet and outlet of the RMP, the temperature at the outlet, and the room temperature were recorded at the end of the experiment. The same procedure was applied for all buffer flow rates and impeller speeds to obtain the pump characteristic curve. Each experiment was repeated at least two times, so each data point shown in the subsequent figures represents the mean value of these measurements. These experimental data, along with the uncertainties of our measuring instruments and calculations, are available in Supplementary Material S.13 and Supplementary Material S.6.

3.3.2. Reaction Experiments

For each experiment involving the reaction, the desired impeller speed of the RMP was first selected, and then the needle valve was adjusted to set the desired buffer flow rate. Next, the acid flow rate was adjusted using the HPLC pump. After adjusting the buffer and acid flow rates and reaching steady state, the vessels containing buffer and acid solutions were weighed before and after a specified period of 2-3 min to determine mass flow rates. Simultaneously, a video was recorded using the high-speed camera. 5 min after the start of the experiment, the inlet pressure, outlet pressure and temperature of the RMP, and room temperature were recorded, and a sample was collected at the outlet of the setup. The sample was analyzed by a UV-vis spectrophotometry immediately after collection to measure the concentration of triiodide. The same procedure was used for all flow rates of acid and buffer solutions. More details on UV calibration and sample preparations for UV calibration are available in Supplementary Material S.7. Each experiment was repeated at least twice, so each data point shown in the subsequent figures represents the mean value of these measurements. For experiments with higher flow rates of acid solution (>10 mL min⁻¹), a second HPLC pump (similar to the first one) was connected in parallel to the first HPLC pump to increase the acid flow rate up to 20 mL min⁻¹. All the experimental data, and uncertainties of the measuring instruments and calculations are included in Supplementary Material S.14 and Supplementary Material S.6.

3.4. Modeling and Calculations

3.4.1. Balance Equations

To describe the product distribution of the VD reaction system in the RMP using the engulfment model, Equation (2.4) must be solved simultaneously for all species involved in the reaction network. An exception is water, which is produced in the iodine–iodate reaction (Reaction (II)). For water, Equation (2.4) does not need to be solved, as its concentration can be assumed constant due to the use of aqueous solutions.

In the kinetic system of the VD reaction proposed by Manzano Martínez *et al.* [27], the iodine-iodide reaction was characterized by the chemical equilibrium constant K_{eq} , allowing the concentration of triiodide (denoted as Q) to be calculated using an algebraic equation. This approach led to a differential-algebraic equation (DAE) system, where the concentration of triiodide was implicitly tied to the equilibrium condition.

In this work, the modeling approach from Fonte *et al.* [43] was applied, where the iodine-iodide reaction was modelled as a set of two separate reactions. This modification enabled the entire reaction system to be described by an ordinary differential equation (ODE) system, rather than a DAE system. The reaction rates for the forward reaction ($k_3 = 5.9 \times 10^9 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and for the backward reaction ($k_4 = 7.5 \times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$) are consistent with the equilibrium constant K_{eq} at 20 °C [44].

In this work, the W-Z-transformation proposed by Bałdyga *et al.* [45] was applied to simplify the solution of the ODE system. Due to the quasi-instantaneous nature of the neutralization reaction, the system is highly stiff, requiring very small time steps and resulting in long computation times. The W-Z-transformation offers an effective way to overcome this issue.

Liu [46] has previously demonstrated the application of the W-Z-transformation to the VD reaction system within the framework of the interaction-by-exchange-with-the-mean (IEM) micromixing model. However, to the best of the authors' knowledge, this transformation has not yet been applied to the VD reaction system in the context of the engulfment model. This work therefore presents such an application for the first time.

The core of the W-Z-transformation is that the first reaction is treated as instantaneous. As a consequence, species A and B cannot coexist in the system at the same time. Consequently, it is necessary to only consider the concentration difference between A and B, as proposed by Burke *et al.* [47]. This approach combines the balance equations in a way that eliminates the reaction term of the first reaction. By doing so, new composition variables, denoted as w and z , are introduced, as defined by Equation (3.1) and Equation (3.2). This transformation is known as the W-Z-transformation [45].

$$w = c_A - c_B \quad (3.1)$$

$$z = c_B - c_R \quad (3.2)$$

Since the reaction rates of the first and second reaction depend on the concentration c_A of hydrogen ions and the concentrations c_B of dihydrogen borate, c_A and c_B must be expressed in

terms of the new variable w . Since A and B cannot coexist, the positive part of w corresponds to the concentration c_A (Equation (3.3)) whereas the negative part of w corresponds to the concentrations c_B (Equation (3.4)).

$$c_A = \frac{|w| + w}{2} \quad (3.3)$$

$$c_B = \frac{|w| - w}{2} \quad (3.4)$$

The concentration of boric acid (R) can be calculated according to Equation (3.5).

$$c_R = z - \frac{|w| - w}{2} \quad (3.5)$$

A full description of this procedure is provided in Supplementary Material S.9. For further details, refer to [45]. The resulting balance equations for the reaction zone according to Equation (2.4) are given by Equation (3.6) to Equation (3.11).

$$\frac{dw^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(w^{(2)} - w^{(1)} \right) - 6k_2 \left(\frac{|w^{(1)}| + w^{(1)}}{2} \right)^2 c_C^{(1)} c_D^{(1)2} \quad (3.6)$$

$$\frac{dc_C^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(c_C^{(2)} - c_C^{(1)} \right) - k_2 \left(\frac{|w^{(1)}| + w^{(1)}}{2} \right)^2 c_C^{(1)} c_D^{(1)2} \quad (3.7)$$

$$\frac{dc_D^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(c_D^{(2)} - c_D^{(1)} \right) - 5k_2 \left(\frac{|w^{(1)}| + w^{(1)}}{2} \right)^2 c_C^{(1)} c_D^{(1)2} - k_3 c_D^{(1)} c_P^{(1)} + k_4 c_Q^{(1)} \quad (3.8)$$

$$\frac{dc_P^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(c_P^{(2)} - c_P^{(1)} \right) + 3k_2 \left(\frac{|w^{(1)}| + w^{(1)}}{2} \right)^2 c_C^{(1)} c_D^{(1)2} - k_3 c_D^{(1)} c_P^{(1)} + k_4 c_Q^{(1)} \quad (3.9)$$

$$\frac{dc_Q^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(c_Q^{(2)} - c_Q^{(1)} \right) + k_3 c_D^{(1)} c_P^{(1)} - k_4 c_Q^{(1)} \quad (3.10)$$

$$\frac{dz^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(z^{(2)} - z^{(1)} \right) \quad (3.11)$$

3.4.2. Estimation of the Energy Dissipation Rate

According to the model, the engulfment rate is directly correlated with the local energy dissipation rate. In order to compare the experimental observations with the model predictions, the local energy dissipation rate present in the RMP near the acid inlet must therefore be estimated for the chosen operation condition (e.g. the impeller speed). Given the unavailability of simple direct measurements of the local energy dissipation rate, this study employed an estimation approach by calculating the integral energy dissipation rate.

In pump systems, only a portion of the electrical power input is converted into hydraulic power, as a certain amount of the input energy is inevitably dissipated due to mechanical and viscous friction. In the RMP, due to the high Reynolds numbers and the associated high turbulence

levels, it is reasonable to assume that the majority of the dissipated power is utilized to generate and sustain turbulence and mixing within the fluid, rather than to overcome mechanical friction. In our experiments, the Reynolds numbers were calculated using Equation (3.12) and ranged between 19 800 and 55 350.

$$\text{Re} = \frac{ND^2}{\nu} \quad (3.12)$$

Here, N and D represent impeller speed and impeller diameter, respectively. According to Kolmogorov's turbulence theory [48], energy cascades from large eddies to smaller ones until it is finally dissipated as heat at the smallest scales. This dissipation occurs at the microscale within the fluid, resulting in localized heating that is negligible in terms of its effect on the bulk fluid temperature. Based on this assumption, the energy dissipation rate in the RMP can be estimated using the hydraulic power output and the hydraulic efficiency of the pump, as described in Equation (3.13). The derivation of Equation (3.13) can be found in Supplementary Material S.10.

$$\epsilon = \left(\frac{1}{\eta} - 1 \right) \frac{\Delta p \dot{V}^{(2)}}{\rho \dot{V}^{(0)}} \quad (3.13)$$

Here, η , Δp , and ρ are the hydraulic efficiency of the RMP, the static pressure difference between the outlet and inlet of the RMP, and the density of the fluid, respectively. The hydraulic efficiency of the pump describes the ratio of the hydraulic power output of the pump to the mechanical power supplied by the impeller. Based on our previous calculations [36, 49], a hydraulic efficiency of 10 % was considered.

3.4.3. The Segregation Index

The segregation index, often denoted as X_S , is a dimensionless parameter widely used to assess the quality of mixing in fast competitive reaction systems. It quantifies the extent to which an undesired side reaction occurs and serves as a measure of the deviation of a real system from the ideal case of perfect micromixing. The segregation index is defined by Equation (3.14), where S_{II} is the selectivity of reactant A toward product Q formed in the side reaction (Reaction (II)), and $S_{\text{II}}^{\text{ST}}$ represents the corresponding selectivity under the assumption of infinitely slow micromixing [39, 50].

$$X_S = \frac{S_{\text{II}}}{S_{\text{II}}^{\text{ST}}} \quad (3.14)$$

The selectivity S_{II} of the side reaction is determined using Equation (3.15), where $\dot{V}^{(1)}$ represents the acid volumetric flow rate and \dot{V}^{out} denotes the total outlet volumetric flow rate ($\dot{V}^{\text{out}} = \dot{V}^{(1)} + \dot{V}^{(2)}$). Additionally, $c_A^{(1)\text{in}}$ is the inlet concentration of the acid flow, while c_P^{out} and c_Q^{out} represent the outlet concentrations of iodine (P) and triiodide (Q).

$$S_{\text{II}} = 2 \frac{\dot{V}^{\text{out}} (c_P^{\text{out}} + c_Q^{\text{out}})}{\dot{V}^{(1)} c_A^{(1)\text{in}}} \quad (3.15)$$

The reference value $S_{\text{II}}^{\text{ST}}$ corresponds to the theoretical selectivity of the side reaction under the condition of infinitely slow mixing. In such cases, the selectivity depends solely on the inlet concentrations $c_B^{(2)\text{in}}$ and $c_C^{(2)\text{in}}$ of borate (B) and iodate (C) ions as well as the stoichiometry of

the reaction. This reference value can be calculated using Equation (3.16) [50]. The derivation of Equation (3.16) is provided in Supplementary Material S.11.

$$S_{\text{II}}^{\text{ST}} = \frac{6c_{\text{C}}^{(2)\text{in}}}{6c_{\text{C}}^{(2)\text{in}} + c_{\text{B}}^{(2)\text{in}}} \quad (3.16)$$

Since the neutralization reaction occurs almost instantaneously, the selectivity of the side reaction approaches zero under conditions of instantaneous mixing. In contrast, for extremely slow mixing, the selectivity approaches the limiting selectivity. Consequently, the segregation index in this case ranges from 0 to 1, where 0 corresponds to instantaneous mixing and 1 represents infinitely slow mixing. Intermediate values of the segregation index indicate partial mixing, reflecting a state between these two extremes.

In Equation (3.15) and Equation (3.16), to calculate the segregation index, all the parameters except the concentrations of iodine and triiodide are known. The concentration of triiodide is measured using UV-vis measurements (Supplementary Material S.7), while the concentration of iodine cannot be directly determined. Since iodine participates in an equilibrium reaction forming triiodide, its concentration is linked to the triiodide concentration through a mass balance equation (Equation (3.17)):

$$\dot{V}^{\text{out}} c_{\text{D}}^{\text{out}} = \dot{V}^{(2)} c_{\text{D}}^{(2)\text{in}} - \dot{V}^{\text{out}} \left(\frac{5}{3} (c_{\text{P}}^{\text{out}} + c_{\text{Q}}^{\text{out}}) + c_{\text{Q}}^{\text{out}} \right) \quad (3.17)$$

Using this relation and the equilibrium constant K_{eq} (see Supplementary Material S.1), a second-order polynomial can be derived, where the iodine concentration is the only unknown variable (Equation (3.18)).

$$\frac{5}{3} \dot{V}^{\text{out}} c_{\text{P}}^{\text{out}2} + \left(\frac{8}{3} \dot{V}^{\text{out}} c_{\text{Q}}^{\text{out}} - \dot{V}^{(2)} c_{\text{D}}^{(2)\text{in}} \right) c_{\text{P}}^{\text{out}} + \frac{\dot{V}^{\text{out}} c_{\text{Q}}^{\text{out}}}{K_{\text{eq}}} = 0 \quad (3.18)$$

By solving this polynomial equation, the iodine concentration can be determined.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Pump Characteristic Curve

Figure 4.1 shows the characteristic curve of the reaction mixing pump, which was obtained based on the experimental procedure described in Section 3.3.1. This figure illustrates the pressure difference between the inlet and outlet of the RMP at different flow rates of the buffer solution and various impeller speeds. As anticipated, an increase in impeller speed results in an increase in pressure difference, under constant volumetric flow rate conditions of the buffer solution. Conversely, at a constant impeller speed, an increase in the buffer flow rate results in a decrease in the pressure difference. As seen in this figure, the changes from 80 % to 100 % of the maximum impeller speed do not have a significant effect on the pump characteristic curve.

In all figures of the results and discussion section, the experimental data represent the mean values of the measurements, and the error bars indicate the mean absolute errors.

Figure 4.1.: The characteristic curve of the RMP as a function of the buffer flow rate at different impeller speeds N . The numbers in parentheses are percentages of the maximum impeller speed. Dashed lines were obtained through linear regression and are included as a guide to the eye to illustrate the overall trend.

4.2. Reaction Experiments

4.2.1. Effect of Acid Flow Rate

Figure 4.2 shows the effect of acid feed rate on the segregation index at different impeller speeds. The abscissa represents the acid-to-buffer flow ratio, while the flow rate of the buffer solution is

constant (4Lh^{-1}), and only the acid flow rate was varied.

Three regimes can be distinguished in Figure 4.2. In the regime of a high acid-to-buffer flow ratio (0.10–0.15, indicated by a light blue background colour), a decrease in the acid feed rate leads to a decrease in the segregation index. This decrease is observed at all impeller speeds. We hypothesize that the product distribution in this regime is determined by mesomixing, since a decreasing acid flow rate leads to a lower local acid concentration that disperses more quickly. This reasoning is consistent with the conclusions of other researchers [2, 6, 51–55]. We refer to this regime as the ‘mesomixing regime’ in the following.

When the acid feed rate decreases further, the segregation index reaches a minimum. This behaviour is observed for all impeller speeds, as indicated by the light green background colour in Figure 4.2. We hypothesize that micromixing determines the product distribution in this regime. To support this, we compared our experimental segregation index results with predictions from micromixing models. A detailed discussion of this issue can be found in Section 4.2.3.

Interestingly, decreasing the acid feed rate further increases the segregation index. However, it is generally expected that the feed rate would have no effect in the ‘micromixing regime’. This regime is highlighted in light red in Figure 4.2. This phenomenon is somewhat similar to the effects observed by Assirelli *et al.* [56]. They increased the diameter of the feed tube and observed an increase in the segregation index in a semi-batch reactor agitated by a Rushton turbine. Although a different parameter was altered, both a larger capillary diameter and a lower volumetric flow rate result in reduced flow velocity within the feed tube. Under these conditions, it is possible that some of the buffer fluid is pushed back into the acid feed capillary due to centrifugal forces in the RMP. This phenomenon is known as ‘backmixing’, whereby fluid recirculates into the acid feed capillary. In the backmixing regime, increasing the impeller speed results in a higher segregation index. This observation supports our hypothesis that strong centrifugal forces cause the buffer solution to mix back into the acid feed tube. In contrast, as expected, increasing the impeller speed in the micromixing and mesomixing regimes decreases the segregation index. The segregation index is more sensitive to changes in impeller speed in the mesomixing regime than in the micromixing regime. Figure 4.2 also shows that, as the impeller speed increases, the minimum segregation index shifts from left to right.

4.2.2. Backmixing Regime

In order to examine the hypothesis that the steep increase of the segregation index for low acid flow rates is indeed caused by backmixing into the feed pipe, additional experiments were conducted at higher acid and buffer flow rates. Figure 4.3 shows these experimental data. This figure displays the segregation index as a function of the impeller speed at different volumetric flow rates of acid and buffer solution, while maintaining a constant acid-to-buffer flow rate ratio of 0.014. Based on the observation presented in Figure 4.2, this ratio falls within the possible regime of backmixing.

As demonstrated in Figure 4.3, an increase in impeller speed is observed to correspond with an increase in the segregation index for all acid and buffer flow rates. As shown in Figure 4.3, an increase in impeller speed always results in an increase in the segregation index for all acid and

Figure 4.2.: The effect of acid feed rate on the segregation index at different impeller speeds, and at a constant buffer flow rate of 4 L h^{-1} .

buffer flow rates. This observation supports our hypothesis of backmixing into the feed pipe. Increased impeller speed also leads to greater centrifugal forces being exerted on the fluid in the pump. Centrifugal forces push some fluid element containing the buffer solution into the acid feed pipe, where they react under locally very poor mixing conditions. Consequently, the second and third reactions are more pronounced in this regime, resulting in a higher segregation index on a global scale. It is important to note that the negative impact of higher stirrer speeds on the selectivity is most pronounced at low volumetric flow rates. This phenomenon can be attributed to the observation that a reduced acid volumetric flow rate leads to a decrease in flow velocity within the acid feed pipe. Consequently, there appears to be an increased likelihood of backflow into the feed tube, thereby further substantiating the hypothesis that backflow occurs under these specific conditions. In order to design and scale up RMPs for mixing-sensitive reactions, it is essential to identify and predict the backmixing regime. This will prevent the negative effects of backmixing into the feed pipe on the selectivity.

Figure 4.3.: The segregation index as function of the impeller speed in the backmixing regime at different volumetric flow rates of acid and buffer solutions, while maintaining a constant acid-to-buffer flow rate ratio of 0.014.

4.2.3. Micromixing Regime

In order to test the hypothesis that the product distribution is determined by micromixing at medium flow rates of acid feed, additional experiments were performed at a constant acid-to-buffer flow rate ratio of 0.10 (see Figure 4.2). In this study, the overall feed rate and impeller speed were both varied. Figure 4.4 shows the results of this study. It is evident that increasing impeller speeds, which correspond to higher energy input, results in a decrease of the segregation index to an order of magnitude of 10^{-3} . The segregation index measurements for different overall volumetric flow rates are almost identical within the experimental error. This observation supports the hypothesis of micromixing in this regime, as the reaction selectivity in the case of a micromixing limited process is primarily influenced by the ratio of volumetric flow rates and the local energy dissipation rates. For the lowest feed rate of 7.1 ml/min, a slight increase of the segregation index is observed at the two highest impeller speeds. This finding indicates that the product distribution under these operating conditions is influenced by backmixing due to the relatively low outlet velocity from the feed pipe and the high impeller speed. The segregation

Figure 4.4.: The segregation index as a function of impeller speed in the micromixing regime at different flow rates of acid and buffer solutions, while maintaining a constant acid-to-buffer flow rate ratio of 0.10.

index was predicted for the operation conditions of the experiments shown in Figure 4.4 using the engulfment model described in Section 2.2. In the figure, model predictions are depicted using hollow markers, while the lines are included solely as guide to the eye. It is important to note that the engulfment model is used to predict the segregation index only at the experimental data points and does not generate a continuous curve. This is because the model relies on the corresponding pressure increase and flow rate values to estimate the energy dissipation rates, which are not available between the measured points. As demonstrated in this figure, there is a strong correlation between the experimental data and the model, thereby validating the hypothesis concerning the presence of a micromixing regime at moderate acid-to-buffer flow rate ratios.

The segregation index, like all selectivities, depends on the specific reaction system. To quantify the mixing behavior purely within the micromixing regime, theoretical mixing times are

computed from the experimental data. The necessary correlation between the segregation index and the mixing time is determined using the engulfment model. This correlation is provided in Supplementary Material S.12. Using this correlation, the corresponding mixing time can be determined for each experimental data point. The results are depicted in Figure 4.5. The line represents the micromixing time according to Bałdyga *et al.* [29], while the symbols denote our experimental data in the micromixing regime. For comparison, also the experimental data from Manzano Martínez *et al.* [27] are presented in this figure. They conducted mixing experiments using the VD reaction system in a rotor-stator spinning disc reactor.

As demonstrated in this figure, our experimental findings closely align with the theoretical correlation of the mixing time with the energy dissipation rate. This finding confirms our hypothesis, as outlined in Section 4.2.1, that the mixing process in this regime is limited by micromixing. Furthermore, the ranges of energy dissipation rates and mixing times reported in the present work are comparable to the results reported by Manzano Martínez *et al.* [27]. The discrepancies observed between our findings and those reported by Manzano Martínez *et al.* [27] can be attributed to the utilisation of varying acid concentrations in the respective experiments. In our work, the inlet concentration of acid was 0.05 mol L^{-1} , whereas in [27] it was 0.1 mol L^{-1} .

In addition to Figure 4.5, Table 4.1 also shows a comparison of the performance of different reactors for the VD reaction system. The table shows the order of magnitude of the energy dissipation rate and the order of magnitude of the calculated mixing time based on different micromixing models. Although different acids, acid concentrations, and micromixing models have been used in these studies, the table can provide a rough estimation for comparing different reactors. Although the maximum flow rate of buffer solution in our RMP can be 50 L h^{-1} , the current results are for lower flow rates to reduce the consumption of buffer solution. Consequently, in our RMP, it is anticipated that reduced mixing times can be attained by increasing the flow rate and, consequently, the energy dissipation rates.

Figure 4.5.: Mixing times as a function energy dissipation rates. Lines: calculated micromixing time according to Bałdyga *et al.* [29]. Symbols: \circ - our experimental data obtained in micromixing regime, \square - experimental data from Manzano Martínez *et al.* [27] (The data including the error bars were extracted by a web-based software [57]).

Table 4.1.: Comparison of different reactors.

research group	reactor type	ϵ (W kg^{-1})	t_{mix} (s)	model
Guichardon <i>et al.</i> [21]	stirred vessel	10^{-2} - 10^0	10^{-2} - 10^{-1}	incorporation model
Fang <i>et al.</i> [11]	Kenics mixer	10^{-2} - 10^0	10^{-3} - 10^{-1}	incorporation model
Manzano Martínez <i>et al.</i> [27]	rs-SDR	10^2 - 10^4	10^{-4} - 10^{-3}	engulfment model
Falk <i>et al.</i> [58]	micromixers	10^1 - 10^5	10^{-5} - 10^{-3}	IEM model
this work	RMP	10^1 - 10^3	10^{-2} - 10^{-3}	engulfment model

5. Conclusion and Outlook

In this research, the behavior of a RMP as a reactor for mixing-sensitive reactions was investigated. It was experimentally examined how impeller speed (22-61.5 rps) and feed rate ratios (0.007-0.15) influence the selectivity of the Villermaux-Dushman reaction system in a RMP. At constant impeller speed, three distinct mixing regimes - backmixing, micromixing and mesomixing regime - were observed at low, medium, and high feed rate ratios, respectively. At a constant feed rate ratio, an increase in impeller speed was found to increase selectivity for desired products in the micro- and mesomixing regimes, while it increased selectivity in the backmixing regime. In both the backmixing and mesomixing conditions, selectivity was notably affected by variations in the feed ratio. In contrast, in the micromixing regime, these changes had an insignificant impact on the selectivity.

Furthermore, the engulfment micromixing model was utilized to predict selectivities in the micromixing regime, showing good agreement with our experimental results. In order to enhance the numerical stability of the solver, the W-Z-transformation was utilised. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first application of the W-Z-transformation for the Villermaux-Dushman reaction system within the context of the engulfment model.

High energy dissipation rates (on the order of magnitude of 10^3 W/kg) led to short mixing times (on the order of magnitude of 10^{-3} s) and high selectivity for desired products (segregation indices on the order of magnitude of 10^{-3}) within the micromixing regime. This observation highlights the potential of RMPs as effective reactors for mixing-sensitive processes. Given the prevalence of side channel machines in the industry and their demonstrated reliability, it can be assumed that RMPs are generally well accepted in the industry. This innovation could enable process intensification by employing RMPs for both the transport of reaction media and the role of reactors. To extensively utilize this type of reactor, further studies are required to better identify the mixing regimes and their boundaries, so as to control the process conditions to prevent backmixing and increase the potential to work within the micromixing regime.

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Nomenclature

Latin letters

A	hydrogen ion	-
B	dihydrogen borate ion	-
C	iodate ion	-
D	iodide ion	-
R	boric acid	-
P	iodine	-
Q	triiodide ion	-
E	engulfment rate	s^{-1}
$V^{(0)}$	total reactor fluid volume	m^3
$V^{(1)}$	reaction zone volume	m^3
$V^{(2)}$	bulk phase volume	m^3
$\dot{V}^{(0)}$	volumetric flow rate outlet	$m^3 s^{-1}$
$\dot{V}^{(1)}$	volumetric flow rate acid feed	$m^3 s^{-1}$
$\dot{V}^{(2)}$	volumetric flow rate buffer feed	$m^3 s^{-1}$
$X^{(1)}$	volume fraction reaction zone	$m^3 m^{-3}$
$c^{(1)}$	concentration in reaction zone	$mol m^{-3}$
$c^{(2)}$	concentration in bulk phase	$mol m^{-3}$
$c^{(1)in}$	concentration acid feed	$mol m^{-3}$
$c^{(2)in}$	concentration buffer feed	$mol m^{-3}$
R	reaction source term	$mol m^{-3} s^{-1}$
$\Delta V^{(1)}$	volume acid feed element	m^3
$\Delta V^{(2)}$	volume buffer feed element	m^3
Δt	macroscopic time step	s
t_{mix}	micromixing time	s
pH	negative base-10 logarithm of the hydrogen ion activity	-
pK_a	negative base-10 logarithm of the acid dissociation constant	-
k_1	reaction rate coefficient of Reaction (I)	$L mol^{-1} s^{-1}$
k_2	reaction rate coefficient of Reaction (II)	$L^{-4} mol^{-4} s$
k_3	forward reaction rate coefficient of Reaction (III)	$L mol^{-1} s^{-1}$
k_4	backward reaction rate coefficient of Reaction (III)	s^{-1}
K_{eq}	equilibrium constant	$L mol^{-1}$
N	impeller speed	rps
D	impeller diameter	m

continued ...

... continued

η	RMP efficiency	%
Δp	static pressure inlet-outlet RMP	Pa
X_S	segregation index	-
S_{II}	selectivity of Reaction (II) (A towards Q)	-
S_{II}^{ST}	selectivity of Reaction (II) for infinitely slow mixing	-
w	composition variable W-Z-transformation	mol L^{-1}
z	composition variable W-Z-transformation	mol L^{-1}

Greek letters

ϵ	energy dissipation rate	W kg^{-1}
ν	kinematic viscosity	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
α	life time acid element	s
ρ	density	kg m^{-3}

Subscripts

i	species index	-
k	run variable engulfment model	-
end	end of inner iteration	-

Superscripts

Abbreviations

RMP	reaction mixing pump
CSTR	continuous stirred tank reactor
rs-SDR	rotor-stator spinning disk reactor
PMMA	poly(methyl methacrylate)
HPLC	high performance liquid chromatography
HSC	high speed camera
VD	Villermaux-Dushman
DAE	differential-algebraic equation
ODE	ordinary differential equation
IEM	interaction-by-exchange-with-the-mean

S. Supplementary Material

S.1. Kinetic Model of Villiermaux-Dushman Reaction

In the Villiermaux-Dushman reaction system, the first reaction (Reaction (I)) occurs nearly instantaneously with a rate constant $k_1 = 10^{11} \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The second reaction (Reaction (II)) is a fast reaction, which reaction rate r_2 is described by a fifth-order rate law expression as follows [6]:

$$r_2 = k_2 c_A^2 c_C c_D^2 \quad (\text{S.1})$$

In Equation (S.1), c_A , c_C and c_D denote the molar concentrations of hydrogen ion (A), iodate (C) and iodide (D), respectively. The reaction rate coefficient k_2 can be calculated by Equation (S.2):

$$k_2 = k_{2,0} \gamma^4 \quad (\text{S.2})$$

Here, $k_{2,0}$ is the reaction rate coefficient at infinite dilution ($k_{2,0} = 1.12 \times 10^9 \text{ L}^4 \text{ mol}^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and γ is the overall activity coefficient which can be estimated by Equation (S.3) [59]:

$$\log_{10}(\gamma) = -0.51 \left(\frac{\sqrt{I_S}}{\sqrt{1 + I_S}} \right) + \frac{0.06 + a_1 B_m}{(1 + a_2 I_S)^2} + B_m I_S \quad (\text{S.3})$$

In Equation (S.3), $a_1 = 0.6 \text{ L mol}^{-1}$, $a_2 = 1.5 \text{ L mol}^{-1}$ and $B_m = 0.01347 \text{ L mol}^{-1}$ are constants. The ionic strength I_S is calculated by:

$$I_S = \sum_{i=1}^N c_i z_i^2 \quad (\text{S.4})$$

where c_i and z_i are respectively the concentration of ionic species i and its corresponding ionic charge. N corresponds to the number of ionic species in the solution, which in this case is equal to 5 (A, B, C, D, Q). The equilibrium constant of the third reaction (Reaction (III)) is as follows:

$$K_{\text{eq}} = \frac{c_Q}{c_D c_P} \quad (\text{S.5})$$

where c_Q and c_P represent the concentrations of triiodide (Q) and iodine (P), respectively. This equilibrium constant depends on temperature T in K based on the following relation [60]:

$$\log_{10}(K_{\text{eq}}) = \frac{555}{T} + 7.355 - 2.575 \log_{10}(T) \quad (\text{S.6})$$

S.2. Components of the Experimental Setup

Table S.1.: Components of the experimental setup.

component	model	company	country
reaction mixing pump (P1)	HMR020	Fink Chem+Tech GmbH	Germany
flowmeter 1 (FI1)	ROTA L 63/2400	ZÜFLE	Germany
pump head made of PMMA	—	workshops of the University of Kaiserslautern-Landau	Germany
pressure sensor 1 (PR1)	FDAD3301NR	Ahlborn Mess- und Regelungstechnik GmbH	Germany
pressure sensor 2 (PR2)	FDAD3301R	Ahlborn Mess- und Regelungstechnik GmbH	Germany
HPLC pump (P2)	Smartline Pump 1000	KNAUER	Germany
thermocouple (TI1)	—	—	—
data logger	ALMEMO2690	Ahlborn Mess- und Regelungstechnik GmbH	Germany
high-speed camera (HSC)	Os8S3	Imaging Solutions GmbH	Germany
LED light source	Constellation 120E15	Imaging Solutions GmbH	Germany
stabinger viscometer	SVM 3000	Anton Paar	Austria)
UV-vis spectrophotometry	UVmini-1240	Shimadzu	Japan

S.3. Dimensions of the RMP

Figure S.1.: Main dimensions of the impeller and the side channel of the RMP investigated in this study. The arrows indicate the helical flow path of the fluid within the pump.

S.4. Suppliers and Purity of Chemicals

Table S.2.: Suppliers and purity of the chemicals.

chemical	company	purity
sodium hydroxide	Merck	98.0-100.5 %
boric acid	Merck	99.8 %
potassium iodide	Thermo Fisher Scientific	99.0 %
potassium iodate	Bernd Kraft	99.7 %
perchloric acid	Th. Geyer	70.0 %

S.5. Properties of Buffer Solution

Table S.3.: Viscosity and density of buffer solution at different temperatures.

temperature (°C)	density (g cm ⁻³)	viscosity (mPa.s)
10	1.0018	1.3787
15	1.0012	1.2168
20	1.0003	1.0533
25	0.9995	0.961 16
30	0.9980	0.851 82

S.6. Error Discussion

Table S.4 presents the uncertainties of our measuring instruments and calculations. All parameters in this table were measured directly by instruments, except for the flow rate of the buffer solution, the concentrations of acid and buffer components, the energy dissipation rate, the mixing time, and the segregation index, which were calculated. In Table S.4, the uncertainties of direct measurements are those of the instruments, while the uncertainties of the calculated parameters were derived using the following uncertainty propagation formula (Equation (S.7)). In this equation, u is the uncertainty of $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$, which is a function of the parameters x_i .

$$u(f) = \sqrt{\sum_i \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_i} u(x_i) \right)^2} \quad (\text{S.7})$$

In Table S.4, the values of uncertainty for the flow rate of the buffer solution, the energy dissipation rate, the mixing time, and the segregation index are the average values for all experimental data.

S.7. UV Calibration

The concentration of triiodide was measured using a UV-vis spectrometer based on the Beer-Lambert law:

$$c_Q = \frac{A}{\epsilon l} \quad (\text{S.8})$$

where A is the UV absorption of triiodide at a wavelength of 353 nm, at which the absorption is not affected by other compounds in the solution, ϵ is the triiodide extinction coefficient at 353 nm, and l is the optical

Table S.4.: Uncertainties of the measuring instruments and calculations.

parameters	uncertainty
inlet pressure	0.0001 bar
outlet pressure	0.001 bar
outlet temperature	0.01 °C
temperature of environment	0.1 °C
density	0.0001 g cm ⁻³
viscosity	0.000 01 mPa s
mass of buffer solution	0.1 g
mass of acid solution and buffer components	0.01 g
time	0.01 s
volume of buffer solution	300 mL in 25 L
level of buffer flow meter	0.001 m
UV absorption	0.001
flow rate of acid solution	0.001 mL min ⁻¹
flow rate of buffer solution	0.0433 mL min ⁻¹
concentration of NaOH in buffer solution	0.0726 × 10 ⁻³ mol L ⁻¹
concentration of B(OH) ₃ in buffer solution	0.1441 × 10 ⁻³ mol L ⁻¹
concentration of KIO ₃ in buffer solution	0.0288 × 10 ⁻³ mol L ⁻¹
concentration of KI in buffer solution	0.1440 × 10 ⁻³ mol L ⁻¹
concentration of acid solution	2.7223 × 10 ⁻⁴ mol L ⁻¹
energy dissipation rate	1.0052 W kg ⁻¹
mixing time	2.4065 × 10 ⁻⁶ s
segregation index	2.9902 × 10 ⁻⁴

path length of the UV cell (in this case, $l = 1$ cm). Before the main UV absorption measurements, the UV-vis spectrometer was calibrated to determine the extinction coefficient for triiodide.

For calibration, seven standard samples with known triiodide concentrations were prepared, and their UV absorption at 353 nm was measured. Standard solutions were prepared by mixing different volumes of water and aqueous solutions of I₂ (Merck) and KI (the mixing ratios are available in Table S.5). The solutions were prepared using distilled water stripped with nitrogen, and the concentrations of the I₂ and KI stock solutions were 8×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹ and 3×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹, respectively.

I₂ and I⁻ react in equilibrium reaction of the VD reaction system (Reaction (III)) to produce I₃⁻. As mentioned in Section 2.1, this equilibrium reaction is sensitive to temperature. In this work, all UV measurements were performed at room temperature. Table S.5 shows the concentration of I₃⁻ and the

Table S.5.: Volume of stock solutions, triiodide concentration and UV absorption for standard samples.

sample no.	V _D (mL)	V _P (mL)	V _{H₂O} (mL)	c _Q (mol L ⁻¹)	A(-)
1	0	0	100	0	0
2	5	25	70	1.88 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.459
3	10	25	65	3.46 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.862
4	15	25	60	4.81 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.183
5	10	50	40	6.30 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.646
6	15	50	35	8.87 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.301
7	15	75	10	1.23 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.135

values of UV absorption for standard samples at 293 K. The concentration of I₃⁻ (c_Q) is calculated in terms of the conversion of I₂ (X_P) as follows:

$$c_Q = \frac{X_P V_P c_{P0}}{V_{\text{tot}}} \quad (\text{S.9})$$

where V_P , c_{P0} , and V_{tot} are the volume of iodine solution added to the solution, initial concentration of iodine, and total volume of a standard solution $V_{tot} = V_P + V_D + V_{H_2O}$, respectively. In Equation (S.9), X_P is unknown. To calculate it, Equation (S.9) can be substituted into Equation (S.5) as follows:

$$K_{eq} = \frac{c_Q}{c_D c_P} = \frac{X_P V_{tot}}{(1 - X_P)(V_D c_{D0} - V_P X_P c_{P0})} \quad (S.10)$$

where c_{D0} is the initial concentration of KI solution. Considering Equation (S.5) for K_{eq} , by solving Equation (S.10), X_P is calculated, and thus c_Q is obtained using Equation (S.9). Figure S.2 shows the calibration curve for the UV-vis spectrometer. The experimental data points are accurately represented by a linear function derived through least-squares fitting. This result aligns with the anticipated trend, confirming the applicability of the Lambert-Beer law in this context. Based on the slope of the linear function in Figure S.2, the extinction coefficient of $25\,600\text{ L mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was calculated, which is close to the reported values in the literature, as shown in Table S.6.

Figure S.2.: UV calibration curve.

Table S.6.: Extinction coefficient of triiodide at 353 nm.

research group	extinction coefficient ($\text{L mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$)
Fournier <i>et al.</i> [31]	25 900
Gobert <i>et al.</i> [22]	24136
Guichardon <i>et al.</i> [21]	23 959
Pinot <i>et al.</i> [61]	24500
Commenge <i>et al.</i> [20]	26 047
This work	25 600

S.8. Bulk Equation

In the engulfment model, a time step splitting approach is employed to separate the macroscopic time scale t from the micromixing time scale α . For this, the inherently continuous mixing process is discretized. The continuous acid feed is represented as discrete fluid elements that are mixed sequentially. The volume of these fluid elements is determined by the macroscopic time step Δt , and the volumes of the acid ($\Delta V^{(1)}$) and buffer ($\Delta V^{(2)}$) elements are defined by Equations (S.11) and (S.12).

$$\Delta V^{(1)} = \Delta t \dot{V}^{(1)} \quad (S.11)$$

$$\Delta V^{(2)} = \Delta t \dot{V}^{(2)} \quad (\text{S.12})$$

The balance equations for the acid fluid elements are based on the main equation of the engulfment model (Equation (2.4)). These reactions are solved up to $\alpha_{k,\text{end}} = \Delta t$. During the solution of the balance equations for the reaction zone, the concentrations of the surrounding bulk phase are assumed to remain constant. This assumption is justified because the reaction zone occupies only a small volume fraction of the reactor when fast reactions are considered. At the end of this process, the reaction zone has a volume $V^{(1)}(\alpha_{k,\text{end}})$.

Following this, the bulk concentrations for the subsequent acid feed part must be updated. This is achieved by adding a discretized fluid volume of buffer solution to the reactor, which displaces an equivalent volume of the old bulk phase. This process is constrained by $(V^{(1)}(\alpha_{k,\text{end}} = \Delta t) + \Delta V^{(2)} \leq V^{(0)})$. The total amount of species in the reactor at this point is given by Equation (S.13).

$$\underbrace{V^{(0)} c_{i,k+1}^{(2)}}_{\text{whole reactor}} = \underbrace{c_{i,k}^{(2)} \left(V^{(0)} - V_k^{(1)}(\alpha_{k,\text{end}}) - \Delta V^{(2)} \right)}_{\text{bulk phase}} + \underbrace{c_{i,k}^{(1)}(\alpha_{k,\text{end}}) V_k^{(1)}(\alpha_{k,\text{end}})}_{\text{reaction zone}} + \underbrace{c_i^{(2)\text{in}} V^{(2)}}_{\text{fresh buffer}} \quad (\text{S.13})$$

By dividing Equation (S.13) by the reactor volume $V^{(0)}$, the updated bulk concentrations for the next feed part can be calculated using Equation (S.14).

$$c_{i,k+1}^{(2)} = c_{i,k}^{(2)} \left(1 - X_k^{(1)}(\alpha_{k,\text{end}}) - \frac{\Delta V^{(2)}}{V^{(0)}} \right) + c_{i,k}^{(1)}(\alpha_{k,\text{end}}) X_k^{(1)}(\alpha_{k,\text{end}}) + c_i^{(2)\text{in}} \frac{\Delta V^{(2)}}{V^{(0)}} \quad (\text{S.14})$$

S.9. W-Z-Transformation

To model the VD reaction system (Reactions (I)-(III)) using the engulfment model, the equilibrium reaction (Reaction (III)) is represented as two separate reactions: a forward reaction and a backward reaction. This approach yields the following reaction scheme:

The general form of the engulfment model is provided in Equation (2.4) of the main paper. The source term R_i is expressed as the sum of all reactions involving each species, as detailed in Equation (S.15).

$$R_i = \sum_{j=1}^R \nu_{j,i} r_j \quad (\text{S.15})$$

Here, R_i represents the reaction source term, j denotes the respective reaction, N_R is the total number of reactions (in this case, four), i refers to the respective species, and r_j is the reaction rate of reaction j and $\nu_{j,i}$ denotes the stoichiometric coefficient of the reactant i in reaction j . Using this information, the

balance equation for the engulfment model can be expressed as Equation (S.16).

$$\frac{dc_i^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(1 - X^{(1)}\right) \left(c_i^{(2)} - c_i^{(1)}\right) + \sum_{j=1}^{N_R} \nu_{j,i} r_j \quad (\text{S.16})$$

To apply the engulfment model to this reaction system, Equation (S.16) must be solved for all species, participating in the reaction system, resulting in Equations (S.17) to (S.23).

$$\frac{dc_A^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(1 - X^{(1)}\right) \left(c_A^{(2)} - c_A^{(1)}\right) - r_1 - 6r_2 \quad (\text{S.17})$$

$$\frac{dc_B^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(1 - X^{(1)}\right) \left(c_B^{(2)} - c_B^{(1)}\right) - r_1 \quad (\text{S.18})$$

$$\frac{dc_C^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(1 - X^{(1)}\right) \left(c_C^{(2)} - c_C^{(1)}\right) - r_2 \quad (\text{S.19})$$

$$\frac{dc_D^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(1 - X^{(1)}\right) \left(c_D^{(2)} - c_D^{(1)}\right) - 5r_2 - r_3 + r_4 \quad (\text{S.20})$$

$$\frac{dc_P^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(1 - X^{(1)}\right) \left(c_P^{(2)} - c_P^{(1)}\right) + 3r_2 - r_3 + r_4 \quad (\text{S.21})$$

$$\frac{dc_Q^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(1 - X^{(1)}\right) \left(c_Q^{(2)} - c_Q^{(1)}\right) + r_3 - r_4 \quad (\text{S.22})$$

$$\frac{dc_R^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(1 - X^{(1)}\right) \left(c_R^{(2)} - c_R^{(1)}\right) + r_1 \quad (\text{S.23})$$

The reaction rates r_1 to r_4 are given by Equations (S.24) to (S.27).

$$r_1 = k_1 c_A^{(1)} c_B^{(1)} \quad (\text{S.24})$$

$$r_2 = k_2 c_A^{(1)2} c_C^{(1)} c_D^{(1)2} \quad (\text{S.25})$$

$$r_3 = k_3 c_D^{(1)} c_P^{(1)} \quad (\text{S.26})$$

$$r_4 = k_4 c_Q^{(1)} \quad (\text{S.27})$$

At this stage, the equations can already be solved. However, due to the extremely fast neutralization reaction in the Villermaux-Dushman reaction system, the ODE system is highly stiff. This stiffness necessitates a very fine temporal discretization, resulting in long computation times. The issue arises from the reaction rate r_1 of the first reaction, which is included in Equations (S.17), (S.18), and (S.23). To reduce the stiffness of the ODE system, the reaction term r_1 is removed from it.

A practical simplification involves assuming that the first reaction is instantaneous, which significantly reduces the mathematical complexity of the ODE system [45].

When the first reaction is treated as instantaneous, species A and B cannot coexist. Therefore, it is only necessary to consider the concentration difference between A and B at any given time, as proposed by

Burke *et al.* [47]. This is achieved by subtracting Equation (S.18) from Equation (S.17):

$$\frac{dc_A^{(1)}}{d\alpha} - \frac{dc_B^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(1 - X^{(1)} \right) \left(c_A^{(2)} - c_B^{(2)} - \left(c_A^{(1)} - c_B^{(1)} \right) \right) - r_1 - 6r_2 - (-r_1) \quad (\text{S.28})$$

By defining a new composition variable w (Equation (S.29)), a simplified equation (Equation (S.30)) can be derived, which no longer includes the reaction term r_1 .

$$w = c_A - c_B \quad (\text{S.29})$$

$$\frac{dw^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(1 - X^{(1)} \right) \left(w^{(2)} - w^{(1)} \right) - 6r_2 \quad (\text{S.30})$$

Similarly, the reaction rate r_1 can be removed from Equation (S.23) by defining a second composition variable z (Equation (S.31)), leading to Equation (S.32).

$$z = c_B + c_R \quad (\text{S.31})$$

$$\frac{dz^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(1 - X^{(1)} \right) \left(z^{(2)} - z^{(1)} \right) \quad (\text{S.32})$$

With the reaction rate r_1 removed from the ODE system, the concentration c_A is still needed to compute the reaction rate r_2 . Therefore, an inverse relationship between w and c_A must be defined. Given the assumption that the reaction is instantaneous and that A and B cannot coexist, the positive part of w corresponds to the concentration c_A (Equation (S.33)), while the negative part corresponds to the concentration c_B (Equation (S.34)).

$$c_A = \frac{|w| + w}{2} \quad (\text{S.33})$$

$$c_B = \frac{|w| - w}{2} \quad (\text{S.34})$$

Following this approach, the concentration c_R can be expressed as shown in Equation (S.35).

$$c_R = z - \frac{|w| - w}{2} \quad (\text{S.35})$$

By substituting c_A in Equation (S.25) with the expression from Equation (S.33), the complete ODE system of the engulfment model is described by Equations (S.36) to (S.41).

$$\frac{dw^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(w^{(2)} - w^{(1)} \right) - 6k_2 \left(\frac{|w^{(1)}| + w^{(1)}}{2} \right)^2 c_C^{(1)} c_D^{(1)2} \quad (\text{S.36})$$

$$\frac{dc_C^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(c_C^{(2)} - c_C^{(1)} \right) - k_2 \left(\frac{|w^{(1)}| + w^{(1)}}{2} \right)^2 c_C^{(1)} c_D^{(1)2} \quad (\text{S.37})$$

$$\frac{dc_D^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(c_D^{(2)} - c_D^{(1)} \right) - 5k_2 \left(\frac{|w^{(1)}| + w^{(1)}}{2} \right)^2 c_C^{(1)} c_D^{(1)2} - k_3 c_D^{(1)} c_P^{(1)} + k_4 c_Q^{(1)} \quad (\text{S.38})$$

$$\frac{dc_P^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(c_P^{(2)} - c_P^{(1)} \right) + 3k_2 \left(\frac{|w^{(1)}| + w^{(1)}}{2} \right)^2 c_C^{(1)} c_D^{(1)2} - k_3 c_D^{(1)} c_P^{(1)} + k_4 c_Q^{(1)} \quad (\text{S.39})$$

$$\frac{dc_Q^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(c_Q^{(2)} - c_Q^{(1)} \right) + k_3 c_D^{(1)} c_P^{(1)} - k_4 c_Q^{(1)} \quad (\text{S.40})$$

$$\frac{dz^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(z^{(2)} - z^{(1)} \right) \quad (\text{S.41})$$

S.10. Energy Dissipation Rate

Since there are no measurements of the turbulent energy dissipation rates in the RMP available, the energy dissipation rates in the RMP are estimated based on the hydraulic efficiency of the pump. Because the flow rate $\dot{V}^{(1)}$ of the acid feed is small compared to the flow rate $\dot{V}^{(2)}$ of the buffer feed, it is assumed that the influence of the acid feed on the energy dissipation rates in the RMP is negligible. Based on this assumption, the Bernoulli equation is applied from the inlet to the outlet of the pump according to Equation (S.42).

$$p_{\text{in}} + \frac{\rho}{2} u_{\text{in}}^2 + \rho g h_{\text{in}} + \frac{P^{\text{mech}}}{\dot{V}^{(2)}} = p_{\text{out}} + \frac{\rho}{2} u_{\text{out}}^2 + \rho g h_{\text{out}} + \frac{P^{\text{diss}}}{\dot{V}^{(2)}} \quad (\text{S.42})$$

Here, P^{mech} represents the mechanical power transferred from the impeller to the fluid, while P^{diss} corresponds to the energy dissipated within the fluid. Since the diameters of the inlet and outlet are identical, the change in dynamic pressure is negligible, as well as the height difference between the inlet and outlet which is less than 1 cm. Therefore, Equation (S.42) can be simplified to Equation (S.43).

$$P^{\text{diss}} = P^{\text{mech}} - \Delta p \dot{V}^{(2)} \quad (\text{S.43})$$

Now, the energy dissipation rate ϵ is generally defined by Equation (S.44), where $V^{(0)}$ is the reactor volume and ρ is the density of the fluid.

$$\epsilon = \frac{P^{\text{diss}}}{V^{(0)} \rho} \quad (\text{S.44})$$

By combining Equation (S.43) with the definition of the energy dissipation rate given in Equation (S.44), the energy dissipation rate in the RMP can be estimated by Equation (S.45).

$$\epsilon = \frac{P^{\text{mech}} - \Delta p \dot{V}^{(2)}}{V^{(0)} \rho} \quad (\text{S.45})$$

Since the power supplied to the fluid by the impeller is not directly known, it is estimated from the hydraulic efficiency η of the pump according to Equation (S.46).

$$\eta = \frac{\Delta p \dot{V}^{(2)}}{P^{\text{mech}}} \quad (\text{S.46})$$

By combining Equation (S.45) with Equation (S.46), the energy dissipation rate in the RMP can be determined as expressed in Equation (S.47).

$$\epsilon = \left(\frac{1}{\eta} - 1 \right) \frac{\Delta p \dot{V}^{(2)}}{\rho V^{(0)}} \quad (\text{S.47})$$

In this work, the pressure increase Δp and the corresponding volumetric flow rate $\dot{V}^{(2)}$ were measured experimentally and represented as pump curves (Section 3.3.1). To estimate the energy dissipation rate, the hydraulic efficiency of the pump must be specified. For all calculations, a hydraulic efficiency of 10% was assumed. Figure S.3 illustrates the energy dissipation as a function of the buffer flow rate for different impeller speeds

Figure S.3.: Energy dissipation rate in the RMP calculated from the experimentally measured pump characteristic curves for impeller speeds of 31.2 rps, 47.8 rps, and 61.1 rps, assuming a hydraulic efficiency of 10 %.

S.11. Segregation Index

The formula for the segregation index of the Villermaux-Dushman reaction system was introduced by Fournier *et al.* [31]. However, the original work does not provide a derivation of this formula. To address this gap, the authors present a derivation of the segregation index for a generic parallel competitive reaction system. This derivation is intended to clarify the assumptions and illustrate the process involved in obtaining the segregation index. For this purpose, a generic parallel competitive reaction system of the following form is considered:

For simplicity, the derivation is demonstrated using the example of the dilution of a fluid element within a surrounding bulk phase, following the modeling approach of the engulfment model. This concept is illustrated in Figure S.4.

In Figure S.4a, the principle of a single fluid element being diluted in a surrounding bulk phase is shown. This assumption holds particularly well for very low flow rates of the limiting feed, which in this case is the acid. Under such conditions, interactions between fluid particles of different ages can be neglected, simplifying the analysis.

Figure S.4b represents the typical case of fast or intermediate mixing, where the rate of mass transfer from the bulk to the reaction zone is comparable to or faster than the reaction rate within the reaction zone. In this scenario, the selectivity of the reaction system is influenced by both the mixing speed and the reaction kinetics. The first reaction in the system is nearly instantaneous, while the second reaction proceeds at a slower pace, resembling the behavior observed in the VD reaction system. Here, all of the reactant A initially contained within the fluid element reacts with B from the bulk phase, leading exclusively to the formation of the target product R.

Finally, Figure S.4c illustrates the limiting case of infinitely slow mixing, where the mass transfer rate is much slower than the rates of both reactions. In this case, B is completely consumed first due to the

instantaneous reaction. However, due to the slow mass transfer locally only C is present, resulting in A being able to react only with C. Consequently, the selectivity of the reaction system becomes independent of the reaction kinetics and depends solely on the concentration ratios of A and B in the bulk phase.

a) dilution of a fluid element in a bulk phase

b) fast mixing

c) infinitely slow mixing

Figure S.4.: Derivation of the segregation index: a) dilution of a fluid element in a surrounding bulk phase, b) in the case of fast mixing the selectivity is influenced by the reaction kinetics, c) in the case of infinitely slow mixing the selectivity is independent of the reaction kinetics.

The segregation index X_S is defined by Equation (S.48), where S_{II} represents the selectivity of product A toward the unwanted side reaction (Reaction (S.VI)), and S_{II}^{ST} denotes the selectivity under conditions of infinitely slow mixing.

$$X_S = \frac{S_{II}}{S_{II}^{ST}} \quad (S.48)$$

For the considered reaction system (Reactions (S.V) and (S.VI)), the selectivity $S_{II}(t)$ can be determined

at any time t using Equation (S.49).

$$S_{II} = \frac{|\nu_{2,A}| n_P^{(0)}(t) - n_{P,0}^{(0)}}{|\nu_{2,P}| n_{A,0}^{(0)} - n_A^{(0)}(t)} \quad (S.49)$$

Where $n_i^{(0)}$ and $n_{i,0}^{(0)}$ represent the amount of species i in the entire reactor at time t and the initially present amount at $t = 0$, respectively. The amount $n_i^{(0)}$ species i in the reactor is the sum of the amount of species $n_i^{(1)}$ in the reaction zone and $n_i^{(2)}$ in the bulk phase, as described by Equation (S.50).

$$n_i^{(0)} = n_i^{(1)} + n_i^{(2)} \quad (S.50)$$

Using this equation, the selectivity of the experimentally or computationally investigated reaction can be determined. In the case of infinitely slow mixing, the selectivity of the reaction system depends solely on the concentration ratios of the reactants B and C. To account for this effect in the calculation of selectivity, the selectivity can be reformulated in terms of the concentrations of B and C.

To achieve this, the change in the concentration of the product P is expressed in terms of the reaction extents. In this context, the reaction extents ζ_j are connected to the temporal change of the amount of species i by Equation (S.51).

$$n_i^{(0)}(t) = n_{i,0}^{(1)} + n_{i,0}^{(2)} + \sum_{j=1}^{N_R} \nu_{j,i} \zeta_j(t) \quad (S.51)$$

For the reactants A, B, C, and the product P, the corresponding equations are provided in Equations (S.52) to (S.55).

$$n_A^{(0)}(t) = n_{A,0}^{(1)} + n_{A,0}^{(2)} + \nu_{1,A} \zeta_1(t) + \nu_{2,A} \zeta_2(t) \quad (S.52)$$

$$n_B^{(0)}(t) = n_{B,0}^{(1)} + n_{B,0}^{(2)} + \nu_{1,B} \zeta_1(t) \quad (S.53)$$

$$n_C^{(0)}(t) = n_{C,0}^{(1)} + n_{C,0}^{(2)} + \nu_{2,C} \zeta_2(t) \quad (S.54)$$

$$n_P^{(0)}(t) = n_{P,0}^{(1)} + n_{P,0}^{(2)} + \nu_{2,P} \zeta_2(t) \quad (S.55)$$

In the following, the equations are further simplified by incorporating the initial conditions: reactant A is exclusively present in the reaction zone, reactants B and C are initially only present in the bulk phase, and no product P is initially present, as it is formed during the reaction. By combining Equations (S.52) to (S.55) with Equation (S.49), the selectivity can be expressed solely in terms of the change in the amount of substance of the reactants B and C, as shown in Equation (S.56).

$$S_{II}^{ST} = \frac{|\nu_{2,A}|}{|\nu_{2,P}|} \frac{-\frac{\nu_{2,P}}{\nu_{2,C}} (n_{C,0}^{(2)} - n_C^{(0)}(t))}{\frac{\nu_{1,A}}{\nu_{1,B}} (n_{B,0}^{(2)} - n_B^{(0)}(t)) + \frac{\nu_{2,A}}{\nu_{2,C}} (n_{C,0}^{(2)} - n_C^{(0)}(t))} \quad (S.56)$$

In this equation, the initial amounts of substances B and C are known. Therefore, only an expression for the temporal change in the amount of substances B and C needs to be derived.

In the case of infinitely slow mixing, the reaction rate is governed by the mass transfer rate \dot{n}_i^{mix} . Consequently, the reaction rate $\dot{\zeta}_1(t)$ of the first reaction is equal to the mass transfer rate of B (Equation (S.57)), while the reaction rate $\dot{\zeta}_2(t)$ of the second reaction corresponds to the mass transfer rate of C (Equation (S.58)).

$$\dot{\zeta}_1(t) = \dot{n}_B^{\text{mix}} \quad (S.57)$$

$$\dot{\zeta}_2(t) = \dot{n}_C^{\text{mix}} \quad (\text{S.58})$$

The mass transfer rate is driven by the mixing of the fluid element with the surrounding bulk phase. During this mixing process, bulk fluid is incorporated into the volume of the reaction zone. The resulting mass transfer rate is described by Equation (S.59)

$$\dot{n}_i^{\text{mix}} = c_i^{(2)} \dot{V}^{\text{mix}} \quad (\text{S.59})$$

By combining Equation (S.59) for B and C with Equations (S.57), (S.58), (S.53) and (S.54) the temporal changes in the amounts of substances B and C in the reactor can be expressed in terms of the initial concentrations of B and C in the bulk phase, as outlined in Equations (S.60) and Equation (S.61).

$$\frac{dn_B^{(0)}}{dt} = -c_B^{(2)} \dot{V}^{\text{mix}} \quad (\text{S.60})$$

$$\frac{dn_C^{(0)}}{dt} = -c_C^{(2)} \dot{V}^{\text{mix}} \quad (\text{S.61})$$

From Equations (S.60) and (S.61), the following relationship can be derived:

$$\frac{dn_B^{(0)}}{dn_C^{(0)}} = \frac{n_{B,0}^{(2)}}{n_{C,0}^{(2)}} \quad (\text{S.62})$$

Integration of Equation (S.62), with the initial condition that $n_C^{(0)}(n_B^{(0)} = n_{B,0}^{(0)}) = n_{C,0}^{(0)}$, yields an explicit expression for the amount of C as a function of the amount of B, as shown in Equation (S.63).

$$n_C^{(0)} = n_B^{(0)} \frac{n_{C,0}^{(2)}}{n_{B,0}^{(2)}} \quad (\text{S.63})$$

By rewriting Equation (S.56) and substituting Equation (S.63) into it, Equation (S.64) can be derived.

$$S_{\text{II}}^{\text{ST}} = \frac{|\nu_{2,A}|}{|\nu_{2,P}|} \frac{\frac{-\nu_{2,P}}{\nu_{2,C}}}{\frac{\nu_{1,A}}{\nu_{1,B}} \left(\frac{n_{B,0}^{(2)} - n_B^{(0)}}{n_{C,0}^{(2)} - n_B^{(0)} \frac{n_{C,0}^{(2)}}{n_{B,0}^{(2)}}} \right) + \frac{\nu_{2,A}}{\nu_{2,C}}} \quad (\text{S.64})$$

Now, Equation (S.64) can be further rewritten to derive Equation (S.65), which depends solely on the initial amounts of substances B and C in the bulk phase. This generic equation enables the calculation of selectivity in the case of total segregation for a parallel competitive reaction system, as outlined in Equations (S.V) and (S.VI).

$$S_{\text{II}}^{\text{ST}} = \frac{\frac{\nu_{2,A}}{\nu_{2,C}} n_{C,0}^{(2)}}{\frac{\nu_{1,A}}{\nu_{1,B}} n_{B,0}^{(2)} + \frac{\nu_{2,A}}{\nu_{2,C}} n_{C,0}^{(2)}} \quad (\text{S.65})$$

The first reaction (Reaction (I)) and the second reaction (Reaction (II)) of the VD reaction system are analogous to the reactions described in Reactions (S.V) and (S.VI). Therefore, Equation (S.65) can be directly applied to calculate the selectivity for infinitely slow mixing for the VD reaction system. To achieve this, the stoichiometric coefficients specific to the VD reaction system are substituted into Equation (S.65):

$$S_{\text{II}}^{\text{ST}} = \frac{\frac{-6}{-1} n_{C,0}^{(2)}}{\frac{-1}{-1} n_{B,0}^{(2)} + \frac{-6}{-1} n_{C,0}^{(2)}} \quad (\text{S.66})$$

Which can be simplified to Equation (S.67), which is equivalent to Equation (3.16) provided by Fournier *et al.* [50].

$$S_{II}^{ST} = \frac{6n_{C,0}^{(2)}}{n_{B,0}^{(2)} + 6n_{C,0}^{(2)}} \quad (S.67)$$

S.12. Mixing Time Correlation

To quantify the mixing behavior of the RMP, mixing times are evaluated. This requires translating the experimentally determined segregation index into the corresponding mixing time. The translation is achieved using a theoretical correlation between the segregation index and mixing time, derived from the engulfment model.

The micromixing behavior in the engulfment model is characterized by the engulfment rate, E , which can be expressed as the reciprocal of the mixing time t_{mix} (Equation (S.68)).

$$E = \frac{1}{t_{mix}} \quad (S.68)$$

By substituting the engulfment rate with the mixing time, the segregation index can be expressed as a function of $X_S(t_{mix})$ rather than $X_S(E)$. The results of the calculated correlation for the Villermaux-Dushman reaction in the RMP are presented in Figure S.5.

Figure S.5.: Theoretical relationship between the segregation index and mixing time, derived using the engulfment micromixing model.

Based on this figure, the mixing time can be expressed as a function of the segregation index. This approach allows the experimentally obtained segregation index to be translated into corresponding theoretical mixing times.

S.13. Pump Characteristics Curve Experiments

Table S.7.: Experimental results from the pump characteristic curve measurements, including flow rates, impeller speeds, and static pressure differences. In certain experiments, the absolute impeller speed was determined using a high-speed camera.

Test No.	$\dot{V}^{(2)}$ (g min ⁻¹)	N (%)	N (rpm)	Δp (bar)	T^{out} (°C)	$T^{\text{environment}}$ (°C)
2410291	72.7	30	1315	0.1043	19.77	18.9
2410292	71.5	30	1337	0.1045	19.77	18.9
2410293	72.7	40	1871	0.2323	20.06	18.9
2410294	69.8	40	1875	0.2330	20.07	18.9
2410295	69.6	50	2432	0.4085	20.49	18.9
2410301	71.6	50	2273	0.3534	20.61	19.0
2410302	72.6	50	2296	0.3642	20.7	19.0
2410303	72.7	60	2866	0.5891	21.43	19.0
2410304	70.8	60	2866	0.5888	21.63	19.1
2410305	68.2	70	3371	0.8518	22.62	19.2
2410306	70.1	70	3383	0.8549	22.7	19.2
2410307	69.9	80	3673	1.0057	23.4	19.4
2410308	68.1	80	3673	1.0027	23.54	19.4
2410309	76.2	90	3686	1.0245	23.3	19.5
24103010	70.9	90	3703	1.0244	23.61	19.5
24103011	73.9	100	3703	1.0179	23.77	19.6
24103012	72.0	100	3600	0.9964	23.6	19.7
24103013	184.2	100	3658	0.9487	21.62	19.8
24103014	182.6	100	3688	0.9723	21.75	19.8
24103015	181.6	90	3673	0.9662	21.89	20.0
24103016	180.1	90	3698	0.9749	21.99	20.0
24103017	184.0	80	3658	0.9541	20.0	22.05
24103018	176.6	80	-	0.9599	22.19	20.1
24103019	185.3	70	-	0.7937	21.95	20.1
24103020	184.6	70	-	0.7996	21.99	20.1
2410311	186.1	60	-	0.4815	19.46	19.2
2410312	186.1	60	-	0.4836	19.53	19.2
2410313	185.4	50	-	0.3071	19.41	19.2
2410314	183.3	50	-	0.3147	19.68	19.4
2410315	182.9	40	-	0.1646	19.61	19.4
2410316	184.1	40	-	0.1724	19.79	19.5
2410317	302.9	100	-	0.9168	20.29	19.6
2410318	300.9	100	-	0.9178	20.53	19.7
2410319	302.9	90	-	0.9136	20.6	19.6
24103110	300.5	90	-	0.9196	21.02	19.7
24103111	301.0	80	-	0.8950	21.03	19.7
24103112	302.8	80	-	0.8930	21.13	19.8
24103113	302.8	70	-	0.7311	21.09	19.8
24103114	302.0	70	-	0.7288	21.15	19.8
24103115	301.0	60	-	0.4919	21.05	19.9
24103116	299.2	60	-	0.4862	21.12	19.9
24103117	306.2	50	-	0.2580	20.71	20.0

Test No.	$\dot{V}^{(2)}$ (g min ⁻¹)	N (%)	N (rpm)	Δp (bar)	T^{out} (°C)	$T^{\text{environment}}$ (°C)
24103118	298.2	50	-	0.2557	20.73	20.0
24103119	432.7	100	-	0.8260	21.05	20.0
24103120	431.6	100	-	0.8272	21.17	20.0
24103121	430.6	90	-	0.8261	21.27	20.1
24103122	436.3	90	-	0.8268	21.41	20.1
24103123	435.3	80	-	0.8106	21.54	20.1
24103124	434.4	80	-	0.8076	21.59	20.1
24103125	436.8	70	-	0.6542	21.52	20.3
24103126	438.4	70	-	0.6561	21.57	20.3
24103127	434.4	60	-	0.4113	21.45	20.3
24103128	436.5	60	-	0.4159	21.46	19.4
24103129	833.7	100	-	0.5134	21.43	19.4
24103130	847.2	100	-	0.5166	21.45	19.6
24103131	835.7	100	-	0.5147	21.45	19.3

S.14. Reactive Experiments

Table S.8.: Experimental conditions for reactive mixing experiments using the Villermaux-Dushman reaction system, along with the resulting triiodide absorption measured via UV-Vis spectroscopy. The buffer and acid solution concentrations remain consistent across all experiments.

Test No.	$\dot{V}^{(2)}$ (g min ⁻¹)	$\dot{V}^{(1)}$ (mL min ⁻¹)	$\dot{V}^{(1)real}$ (mL min ⁻¹)	N (%)	Δp_{stat} (bar)	T^{out} (°C)	$T^{environment}$ (°C)	A (-)	date	Figure 4.2	Figure 4.4	Figure 4.3
2410182	70.89	0.05	0.05	30	0.109	22.0	-	0.099	18.10.2024	x		
2410183	71.28	0.10	0.10	30	0.110	21.8	-	0.094	18.10.2024	x		
2410184	74.12	0.50	0.50	30	0.112	21.5	-	0.090	18.10.2024	x		
2410186	75.02	5.00	5.00	30	0.103	21.4	-	0.161	18.10.2024	x		
2410188	75.90	9.99	9.99	30	0.108	21.7	-	1.167	18.10.2024	x		
2411042	70.10	2.50	2.50	50	0.383	20.5	18.8	0.167	04.11.2024	x		
2411043	69.41	5.00	5.00	50	0.387	20.6	18.8	0.136	04.11.2024	x		
2411045	70.66	5.00	5.00	70	0.858	22.1	18.9	0.223	04.11.2024	x		
2411051	69.38	2.50	2.50	70	0.815	21.8	19.3	0.266	05.11.2024	x		
2411055	70.54	0.50	0.50	70	0.843	22.1	19.3	0.113	05.11.2024	x		
2411071	78.83	0.50	0.49	100	1.016	22.5	18.5	0.103	07.11.2024	x		
24110711	70.11	0.50	0.49	50	0.385	20.9	18.9	0.077	07.11.2024	x		
24110713	72.87	2.50	2.33	50	0.377	20.7	18.9	0.162	07.11.2024	x		
2411073	68.78	2.50	2.30	100	1.044	22.9	18.7	0.297	07.11.2024	x		
2411074	68.84	5.00	4.57	100	1.055	22.7	18.8	0.225	07.11.2024	x		
2411076	72.07	9.99	8.96	100	1.061	22.7	18.8	1.270	07.11.2024	x		
2411077	71.11	0.50	0.49	70	0.851	22.2	18.8	0.107	07.11.2024	x		
2411078	69.29	2.50	2.31	70	0.856	22.2	18.9	0.267	07.11.2024	x		
2411079	68.25	5.00	4.60	70	1.031	22.2	18.9	0.215	07.11.2024	x		
2411081	71.17	5.00	4.58	50	0.341	19.8	18.3	0.125	08.11.2024	x		
24110811	72.62	7.50	6.86	30	0.105	19.6	18.3	0.406	08.11.2024	x		
2411083	72.62	9.99	8.99	50	0.351	20.2	18.3	0.559	08.11.2024	x		
2411084	70.91	5.00	4.57	30	0.103	19.9	18.3	0.217	08.11.2024	x		
2411085	68.62	2.50	2.33	30	0.104	19.8	18.5	0.095	08.11.2024	x		
2411087	71.15	2.50	2.50	100	1.037	22.7	18.5	0.289	08.11.2024	x		

Test No.	$\dot{V}^{(2)}$ (g min ⁻¹)	$\dot{V}^{(1)}$ (mL min ⁻¹)	$\dot{V}^{(1)real}$ (mL min ⁻¹)	N (%)	Δp_{stat} (bar)	T^{out} (°C)	$T^{environment}$ (°C)	A (-)	date	Figure 4.2	Figure 4.4	Figure 4.3
2411088	66.39	5.00	4.58	100	1.030	22.6	18.5	0.239	08.11.2024	x		
24111210	73.75	0.50	0.49	100	0.983	22.6	19.2	0.097	12.11.2024	x		
2411122	71.11	2.50	2.29	70	0.824	22.2	19.2	0.286	12.11.2024	x		
2411123	74.38	0.50	0.49	70	0.843	22.3	19.2	0.095	12.11.2024	x		
2411124	71.56	9.99	8.80	50	0.343	20.6	19.2	0.542	12.11.2024	x		
2411125	71.72	0.50	0.50	50	0.356	20.8	19.4	0.081	12.11.2024	x		
2411126	70.72	2.50	2.34	30	0.106	20.4	19.5	0.110	12.11.2024	x		
2411128	67.91	0.50	0.50	30	0.108	20.5	19.5	0.093	12.11.2024	x		
2411211	70.04	9.99	8.71	100	0.953	21.3	18.1	1.406	21.11.2024	x		
2411212	72.74	9.99	8.72	70	0.794	20.9	18.1	0.306	21.11.2024	x		
2411213	71.58	9.99	8.73	50	0.350	19.8	18.1	0.479	21.11.2024	x		
2411218	73.54	9.99	8.60	70	0.790	20.9	18.3	0.267	21.11.2024	x		
2411219	72.66	9.99	8.59	30	0.104	19.5	18.3	1.265	21.11.2024	x		
24120412	72.33	9.99	8.91	70	0.818	21.3	17.4	0.324	04.12.2024	x		
24120413	71.98	9.99	8.83	50	0.353	20.2	17.5	0.500	04.12.2024	x		
2410187	69.25	7.50	7.50	30	0.116	21.8	-	0.459	18.10.2024	x	x	
2411044	66.24	7.50	7.50	50	0.386	20.7	18.8	0.245	04.11.2024	x	x	
2411053	70.26	7.50	7.50	70	0.824	21.9	19.3	0.208	05.11.2024	x	x	
24110710	69.41	7.50	6.85	70	0.855	22.2	18.9	0.205	07.11.2024	x	x	
2411075	69.44	7.50	6.81	100	1.063	22.8	18.8	0.222	07.11.2024	x	x	
2411082	71.30	7.50	6.85	50	0.592	20.0	18.3	0.212	08.11.2024	x	x	
2411089	74.38	7.50	6.88	100	1.037	22.5	18.6	0.202	08.11.2024	x	x	
24120410	71.41	7.50	6.95	30	0.100	19.4	18.5	0.460	04.12.2024	x	x	
2410161	71.54	1.00	1.00	30	0.098	21.6	-	0.121	16.10.2024	x		x
2410185	72.29	1.00	1.00	30	0.101	21.2	-	0.120	18.10.2024	x		x
2411041	72.02	1.00	1.00	50	0.360	20.2	18.5	0.135	04.11.2024	x		x
2411046	67.77	1.00	1.00	70	0.864	22.2	18.8	0.217	04.11.2024	x		x
2411052	69.55	1.00	1.00	70	0.798	21.6	19.3	0.200	05.11.2024	x		x
2411056	71.41	1.00	1.00	100	1.019	22.8	19.3	0.219	05.11.2024	x		x

Test No.	$\dot{V}^{(2)}$ (g min ⁻¹)	$\dot{V}^{(1)}$ (mL min ⁻¹)	$\dot{V}^{(1)real}$ (mL min ⁻¹)	N (%)	Δp_{stat} (bar)	T^{out} (°C)	$T^{environment}$ (°C)	A (-)	date	Figure 4.2	Figure 4.4	Figure 4.3
24110712	71.25	1.00	0.97	50	0.379	20.8	18.9	0.146	07.11.2024	x		x
2411072	74.30	1.00	0.95	100	1.041	22.6	18.6	0.201	07.11.2024	x		x
2411086	72.32	1.00	0.96	100	1.025	22.5	18.5	0.213	08.11.2024	x		x
2411135	70.87	1.00	0.97	70	0.841	22.4	19.3	0.198	13.11.2024	x		x
2411271	185.6	19.79	18.11	100	0.897	19.8	18.2	0.105	27.11.2024		x	
2411272	181.9	19.79	17.78	70	0.714	19.7	18.2	0.141	27.11.2024		x	
2411273	185.8	19.79	18.07	50	0.299	19.4	18.2	0.270	27.11.2024		x	
2411274	187.7	19.79	18.35	40	0.153	19.3	18.2	0.392	27.11.2024		x	
2411275	124.5	13.09	12.22	100	0.964	20.9	18.9	0.093	27.11.2024		x	
2411276	134.1	13.09	12.29	70	0.776	20.5	18.9	0.098	27.11.2024		x	
2411277	122.2	13.09	12.22	50	0.334	19.9	19.1	0.230	27.11.2024		x	
2411278	127.3	13.09	12.18	40	0.178	19.7	19.1	0.356	27.11.2024		x	
2412041	118.9	13.09	12.44	100	0.951	20.1	17.9	0.102	04.12.2024		x	
2412042	115.4	13.09	11.89	70	0.773	19.9	17.9	0.111	04.12.2024		x	
2412043	125.9	13.09	12.47	50	0.321	19.3	18.0	0.212	04.12.2024		x	
2412044	129.0	13.09	12.39	40	0.177	19.1	18.0	0.321	04.12.2024		x	
2412045	175.8	19.79	17.90	100	0.961	19.8	18.0	0.112	04.12.2024		x	
2412046	183.1	19.79	18.43	70	0.760	19.5	18.2	0.121	04.12.2024		x	
2412047	182.5	19.79	18.25	50	0.309	19.0	18.2	0.260	04.12.2024		x	
2412048	181.6	19.79	18.02	40	0.161	18.9	18.4	0.405	04.12.2024		x	
2411131	186.0	2.75	2.55	100	0.941	20.5	19.2	0.093	13.11.2024			x
2411132	177.4	2.75	2.60	70	0.757	20.4	19.2	0.091	13.11.2024			x
2411133	180.8	2.75	2.58	50	0.321	19.8	19.2	0.053	13.11.2024			x
2411134	178.2	2.75	2.59	40	0.180	19.7	19.3	0.033	13.11.2024			x
2411136	298.5	4.50	4.13	100	0.916	20.1	19.4	0.035	13.11.2024			x
2411137	299.3	4.50	4.16	50	0.303	19.6	19.4	0.012	13.11.2024			x
2411141	304.0	4.50	4.13	70	0.648	19.5	18.7	0.026	14.11.2024			x
2411142	184.1	2.75	2.58	100	0.990	20.4	18.7	0.097	14.11.2024			x
2411143	175.7	2.75	2.61	40	0.170	19.4	18.7	0.035	14.11.2024			x

Test No.	$\dot{V}^{(2)}$ (g min ⁻¹)	$\dot{V}^{(1)}$ (mL min ⁻¹)	$\dot{V}^{(1)real}$ (mL min ⁻¹)	N (%)	Δp_{stat} (bar)	T^{out} (°C)	$T^{environment}$ (°C)	A (-)	date	Figure 4.2	Figure 4.4	Figure 4.3
2411201	168.6	2.75	2.52	70	0.819	20.5	18.5	0.085	20.11.2024			x
2411202	185.6	2.75	2.51	50	0.334	20.0	18.5	0.049	20.11.2024			x
2411215	298.5	4.50	4.03	100	0.896	19.1	18.2	0.036	21.11.2024			x
2411216	303.0	4.50	4.14	70	0.696	18.9	18.2	0.028	22.11.2024			x
2411217	292.8	4.50	4.15	50	0.278	18.6	18.2	0.014	23.11.2024			x

